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How ORCID works

Each ORCID iD is a unique 16-digit ID that is generated during the personal registration process → e.g. [0000-0002-1825-0097](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1825-0097)
Your ORCID iD is linked to your publications during the registration or submission processes of research journals or repositories. Platforms for peer-review processes and grant applications often allow you to link your ORCID iD with your activities. The iD icon - containing the hyperlink to your personal ORCID profile - is usually displayed next to your name:

→ Josiah Carberry <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1825-0097>

How to register

 Create **only one** ORCID iD. During the [registration process](#) you will see already existing profiles.

Enter all spellings and variants of your name including your birth name in your profile.

Add additional information such as employment, education, positions, memberships, funding, and links to other platforms to make your profile meaningful and to use it as your digital business card.

Control options

You retain full control over your ORCID profile and content visibility. Only the individual ORCID iD always remains public. You determine whether you grant read and write rights to linked databases (e.g. Crossref) or to third parties such as publishers. You can activate automatic updates of your publication list in your ORCID profile through links to databases such as Crossref, Datacite, Base and SCOPUS by using the following buttons:

 Search & link

Manually add publications not automatically listed to your profile using the following buttons:

 Add DOI

Advantages of ORCID for scholars and researchers

- ① Your ORCID profile increases the visibility of your research results, independent of institutions and commercial providers.
- ② Your ORCID iD can be linked to research articles, books, research data, software, lectures, and more.
- ③ Clearly identify yourself to publishers, repositories, professional societies, sponsors, third-party funders, or at conferences.
- ④ You are clearly identifiable, independent of name variants, name changes or different spellings.
- ⑤ Transparently communicate your research output to research sponsors, third-party funders and the science community.
- ⑥ Use your ORCID profile including voluntary information as your digital business card for your next career steps.
- ⑦ You can use your ORCID iD and your personal profile indefinitely and free of charge.

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Tim Boxhammer¹
¹GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel

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